

Activity Measurements in Aquo-organic Solvents by Membrane Electrodes

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Attempts have been made to use some electrochemically responsive clay membranes for cationic-activity measurements in aquo-organic solvents. With aquo-ethanolic solutions cationic activity measurement up to 75% ethanol has been found quite possible, though the range of validity of the Nernst equation is comparatively narrow with respect to aqueous solutions. With aquo-glycol solutions, measurements up to 20% glycol is possible, but at higher glycol concentrations the membranes become more or less unresponsive. The electrical resistance of such membranes in aquo-organic solvents is also very much high in comparison to aqueous solutions.

Use of clay-membrane electrodes for the measurement of ionic activities in aqueous solution is well established either singly or in a mixture of cations^{1,2}, but no attempt seems to have been made for the measurement of ionic activities in aquo-organic solvents. The electrochemical performance of membrane electrodes is considered to be dependent on the exchange characteristics of minerals used as the membrane material. Chatterjee³ has shown that to a certain extent the exchange behaviour of clay minerals in water-ethanol mixtures is similar to that in the aqueous solutions. It may therefore be expected that the same membranes, which perform well in aqueous solutions, may be used in aquo-organic solvents, if proper care is taken. It is with this idea that membrane electrodes have been used for the measurement of ionic activities in aquo-organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set up was similar to those reported earlier⁷. Only those clay membranes were used which performed well in aqueous system. Electrical resistance of such membranes in aquo-organic solvents was measured as with aqueous system. For the activities of cations in aquo-organic solvents, these data were calculated, using activity coefficient of cations in aqueous solution with the help of the Debye-Hückel limiting equation after applying proper correction for the dielectric constant of the aquo-organic solvents. The values of dielectric constants for aquo-organic solvents were taken from the tables given by Peakins and French⁴ and Owia⁵. No other correction in the activity coefficient data was, however, applied since most of the solutions used were dilute.

1. Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155; 1949, **52**, 1284.
2. Bose, *J. Ind. Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, **3**, 65, 109.
3. Chatterjee, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 395.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2589.
5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 1587.

The Ag-AgCl electrode was standardised before use. For this purpose, a cell of the following type:

was set up with varying concentrations of HCl in various ethanol-water media and the E.M.F. values were noted as recorded in Table II. The E.M.F. values were then plotted against activity of Cl^- . In the measurements with the membrane electrode, using the Ag-AgCl electrode, the E.M.F. corresponding to any Cl^- activity was read from the graph, Cl^- activity on one side of the membrane being the same in the above cell.

TABLE II
Temp. = 30°. Ag-AgCl electrode.

25% Ethanol + 75% water. HCl conc. E. M. F. obs. $a_{\text{H}^+}, a_{\text{Cl}^-}$		50% Ethanol + 50% water. HCl conc. E. M. F. obs. $a_{\text{H}^+}, a_{\text{Cl}^-}$		25% Water + 75% ethanol. HCl conc. E. M. F. obs. $a_{\text{H}^+}, a_{\text{Cl}^-}$	
0.014980	0.3627mv	0.035420	0.3628mv	0.016070	0.3611mv
0.019300	0.4072	0.018930	0.3937	0.007437	0.4032
0.008770	0.4433	0.008290	0.4296	0.014023	0.4351
0.004540	0.4843	0.004360	0.4648	0.001704	0.4791
0.001863	0.5301	0.001810	0.5036	0.0009016	0.5111
0.000955	0.56475	0.000937	0.5406	..	..
0.000500	0.6040	..	..	..	..
0.000200	0.6380	..	..	..	..

The values of $a_{\text{H}^+}, a_{\text{Cl}^-}$, calculated in this way from the observed E. M. F. s in 25, 50 and 75% ethanol solutions are recorded in Tables I and III. Similar measurements made in 20, 40, and 60% glycol media are shown in Tables IV and V. It is assumed here that the Ag-AgCl electrode, which is good for measurements in ethanol-water medium, will also behave normally in glycol-water medium. No separate test of validity in glycol-water medium was made.

TABLE III
Temp. = 30°. Ag-AgCl electrode.

$\frac{a_{\text{Cl}^-}^{\text{inside}}}{a_{\text{Cl}^-}^{\text{outside}}}$	E. M. F. (in mv).		Observed by membrane.	Theoretical.
	Total obs.	Due to diff. in Cl^- activity.		
25% Ethanol + 75% water mixture.				
0.0083/0.000285	43.2	32.1	11.1	13.2
0.00083/0.00233	45.4	32.1	13.3	13.2
0.0063/0.00233	45.8	33.0	12.8	12.7
0.0063/0.0166	45.7	33.7	12.0	11.8
50% Ethanol + 50% water mixture.				
0.018/0.00072	42.5	31.0	11.5	11.6
0.0018/0.00412	42.4	31.6	10.8	10.6
0.00412/0.00874	35.2	26.9	8.3	9.3
75% Ethanol + 25% water mixture.				
0.0011/0.00055	36.5	28.2	8.3	8.4
0.0011/0.00178	37.2	31.2	6.0	6.2

TABLE IV

Temp. = 30°. Ag-AgCl electrode.

$\frac{a_{\text{K}^+ \text{ inside}}}{a_{\text{K}^+ \text{ outside}}}$	E. M. F. (in mv).		Observed by membrane.	Theoretical.
	Total obs.	Due to diff. in Cl ⁻ activity.		
20% Glycol + 80% water mixture.				
0.000999/0.0003324	57.0	28.6	29.0	28.6
0.000999/0.00208	57.4	28.6	28.6	28.6
0.00832/0.00298	57.1	28.6	28.5	28.6
0.00832/0.0285	57.1	28.6	28.5	28.6
0.0793/0.0285	53.5	28.6	24.9	28.6
40% Glycol + 60% water mixture.				
0.00099/0.00033	57.4	28.6	28.6	28.6
0.00099/0.00295	57.2	28.6	28.6	28.6
0.0087/0.00295	57.2	28.6	28.6	28.6
0.0087/0.0257	54.1	28.6	25.5	28.6
80% Glycol + 20% water mixture.				
0.00033/0.00011	54.0	28.6	25.4	28.6
0.00033/0.000985	57.4	28.6	28.8	28.6
0.0029/0.000985	55.6	28.6	28.0	28.6

TABLE V

$\frac{a_{\text{Ca}^{2+} \text{ inside}}}{a_{\text{Ca}^{2+} \text{ outside}}}$	E. M. F. (in mv).		Observed by membrane.	Theoretical.
	Total obs.	Due to diff. in Cl ⁻ activity.		
20% Glycol + 80% water mixture.				
0.000296/0.000999	43.0	28.0	14.4	14.3
0.000296/0.000883	42.9	28.0	14.3	14.3
0.00261/0.000883	48.4	32.6	15.8	15.8
0.00261/0.00763	39.4	26.7	12.7	12.6
0.0222/0.00763	39.4	34.6	4.8	13.9
40% Glycol + 60% water.				
0.000287/0.00097	44.0	29.0	14.1	14.1
0.000287/0.00084	44.0	29.9	14.1	14.0
0.00238/0.00084	21.5	> 29.0	< 13.8	13.8
60% Glycol + 40% water mixture.				
0.000277/0.0001	30.5	> 29.0	< 13.8	13.8
0.000277/0.00079	27.0	> 29.0	< 13.8	13.8

TABLE VI

Materials of membrane.	Resistance in ohm/mm thickness in various aquo-organic solvents.				
	25% EtOH + 75% water.	50% EtOH + 50% water.	75% EtOH + 25% water.	25% Glycol + 75% water.	50% Glycol + 50% water.
Padegaon, original (0.5 μ size)					
H-form	7000	9500	15000	4000	6120
Na-form	9500	18000	33000	7835	9870
Ca-form	6500	7200	13000	2835	4400

DISCUSSION

Electrical resistances of the membranes (Table VI) having the same cross section are much higher in aquo-organic solvents than in aqueous system⁷. In aquo-glycol solvent, the resistance is again much less than in aquo-ethanolic system. Probably with the increasing dielectric constant of the medium, the electrical resistance will increase enormously.

Referring to Table I, it is to be seen that the range of validity of the Nernst equation with Padogaon clay-membrane electrode in 25% ethanolic solution is $a_K=0.0003307$ to $a_K=0.07418$, which is less than what obtains in aqueous medium. For 50% ethanolic solution, this range of K^+ activities is 0.00326-0.0539 and for 75% ethanolic solution, it is much less, being 0.000926-0.0191. Incidentally, the molality of K^+ in the measurable range is almost the same in case of 25% and 50% ethanolic solutions and less in case of 75% ethanolic solution.

Results of measurements with Ca^{2+} are shown in Tables III and V. The activity of Ca^{2+} , which is measurable with these membranes, falls within the range of 0.0008-0.0166 in 25% ethanolic solution, 0.000724-0.00412 in 50% ethanolic solution, and 0.00058-0.00173 in 75% ethanolic solution. This means that the molality range of Ca^{2+} , measurable with these membranes, may be almost the same, irrespective of strength of ethanol in the solution, but the range is much less in comparison to the purely aqueous solution.

Results of measurements with glycol-water system are shown in Tables IV and V. With 20% glycol-water solution, the ranges of accurate K^+ and Ca^{2+} activity measurements are 0.0033324-0.02653 and 0.000296-0.00763 respectively. These are thus towards a much lower value than those in 25% ethanol-water system. With 40% and 60% glycol-water systems, the ranges of K^+ activity are respectively 0.00033-0.0087 and 0.00033-0.000985; with Ca^{2+} , the range of satisfactory activity measurements with 40% glycol is 0.000286-0.00084, but in 60% glycol, the membrane is almost unresponsive as an electrode. It might be a fact that in glycol-water system, though the dielectric constant of the mixture is not so much different from pure water, like ethanol-water system, the measurable range in comparison to ethanol-water system is towards much lower activities.

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